

Examining the effect of entrepreneurial work environment on the innovative work behavior of employees

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to examine the effect of an entrepreneurial work environment on the innovative work behaviour of the employees. To support the theories of the study, literature was reviewed. The study follows a research methodology and uses a descriptive assessment and correlational research design. The study used research questionnaires to gather the data and to analyze the data, the weighted mean and Analysis of Variance were used. The study found that entrepreneurial work environments and innovative work behaviour are high. Moreover, there was no correlation between the entrepreneurial work environment and the innovative work behaviour of the employees. Thus, the hypothesis is rejected. It is recommended that further study needs to be done concerning other factors that affect innovative work behaviour.

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Introduction

Managing an organization necessitates not just management, leadership, and financial acumen, but also attention to various facets of the organizational environment. Despite this, management often overlooks the work environment, focusing primarily on broader concerns like company direction and planning. Neglecting the work environment can detrimentally impact both individual and organizational performance (Butt et al., 2015; Wahyuni & Haryanto, 2019).

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Specifically, an entrepreneurial work environment, crucial for fostering creativity and innovation, is frequently disregarded. Such an environment should promote autonomy, risk-taking, and a culture of learning and resilience (Lance et al., 2008). Studies show that an entrepreneurial environment influences employee engagement, firm competitiveness, and performance (Ha et al., 2021; Abun et al., 2022).

Innovation is paramount for economic development, as evidenced by the Global Innovation Index (2021), where the Philippines ranked 51st out of 132 economies. However, innovation requires a conducive work environment to manifest (Kwan et al., 2021).

This study aims to investigate the effect of an entrepreneurial work environment on innovative work behaviors within the context of education, filling a notable research gap. By understanding this relationship, management can better tailor the work environment to inspire employee innovation.

The study comprises an introduction, literature review, research methodology, data presentation and analysis, and result and discussion sections, each serving to deepen understanding and provide actionable insights for management.

Literature Review

The purpose of the literature review is to deepen the understanding of the concepts of entrepreneurship, entrepreneur, entrepreneurial, work environment, entrepreneurial work environment and innovative work behaviour based on the existing literature.

Theoretical and Conceptual Frameworks

The concepts of entrepreneurship, entrepreneur and entrepreneurial

Understanding the term "entrepreneurial" requires grasping the concepts of entrepreneurship and entrepreneur. Entrepreneurship, defined by various sources including Cambridge Dictionary (n.d) and Collins Dictionary, encapsulates the business activities undertaken by individuals to seize new opportunities and generate profits (Schumpeter, 1934; Cornwall, n.d.; Cole, 1959; Ronstadt, 1985; Hisrich et al., 2017).

An entrepreneur, on the other hand, is an individual who undertakes risks to establish businesses based on untapped opportunities, as historically observed in military expeditions ("entreprendre") and outlined by definitions from Merriam-Webster, Cambridge Dictionary, and The New Encyclopedia Britannica (Bhagyashree, n.d; Schumpeter, 1934; McClelland, 1961; Drucker, 1970).

"Entrepreneurial," as an adjective, pertains to qualities essential for entrepreneurial success, such as vision, confidence, opportunity-seeking, and risk-taking, consistent with definitions from Merriam-Webster, Collins Dictionary, and Cambridge Dictionary (Finger & Samwer, 1998; Singh & Rahman, 2013; Kerr et al., 2017).

Characteristics attributed to entrepreneurs include recognizing opportunities, creativity, self-confidence, risk tolerance, and goal orientation, as identified by scholars like Singh and Rahman (2013) and Kerr et al. (2017).

In essence, entrepreneurship embodies the business endeavors of risk-taking individuals, while "entrepreneurial" describes the qualities crucial for entrepreneurial success.

The Concept of Work Environment

The definition of the work environment varies among authors, leading to challenges in determining measurable variables. Raziq and Maulabakhsh (2015) define it as the "interrelationship of employees in their workplace," focusing on working relationships. Salunke (2015) identifies it as "the physical aspect of a workplace," emphasizing physical setups. Kohun (1992) offers a broader scope, defining it as "the bridge between employees and the workplace," encompassing various factors influencing employee activity and performance.

Briner (2000) expands this concept to include physical settings, job characteristics, organizational features, and external factors, providing a comprehensive view. Opperman (2002), as cited by Oludeyi (2015), categorizes the work environment into technical, human, and organizational aspects, including tools, interpersonal dynamics, and leadership.

Numerous studies highlight the work environment's significance in organizational and individual performance. Mihretu and Gopal (2021) found a significant correlation between physical and social work environment and organizational performance. Aftab and Khalid (2020) emphasized the impact of performance-oriented culture on organizational performance. Gitonga and Gachunga (2015) noted the positive correlation between psychological work environment and organizational performance.

Regarding individual performance, Hafeez et al. (2019) and Saidi et al. (2019) observed improved productivity due to positive work environments, while Ollukaran and Gunaseelan (2012) identified the social and professional work environment as predictors of employee performance.

Overall, research underscores the importance of the work environment in organizational management. Neglecting it can demotivate employees and hinder organizational success, emphasizing the need for attention beyond financial incentives. Employees' behavior is significantly influenced by their workplace environment.

Entrepreneurial Work Environment

A conducive work environment, both internal and external, significantly influences organizational and individual performance. External factors like societal values and governmental regulations shape entrepreneurial performance, with a positive environment fostering innovation and growth (Brainkart, 2021; Sudhamathi, 2016). Similarly, the internal environment, surrounding employees, either stimulates or demotivates entrepreneurial behavior (Brainkart, 2021).

An entrepreneurial work environment, characterized by risk-taking, autonomy, and learning from failure, encourages innovation and employee performance (Chadha, 2020; Abun et al., 2021). Organizational factors also impact entrepreneurial behavior and innovation (De Jong et al., 2015; Leblebici, 2012).

Moreover, entrepreneurial motivation is influenced by the entrepreneurial environment, with government support and policies playing a significant role (Wu & Mao, 2020). Enhancing entrepreneurial motivation through such an environment positively impacts business performance (Machmud & Sidharta, 2016; Tedla, 2016).

Comparatively, bureaucratic environments lead to lower job satisfaction compared to non-bureaucratic ones, as autonomy fosters independence and self-efficacy (Adler & Borys, 1996; Langfred & Moye, 2004; Wood & Bandura, 1989). The autonomy inherent in an entrepreneurial work environment directly affects motivation and satisfaction, influencing overall performance (Cantarelli et al., 2016; Saidi et al., 2019).

Entrepreneurial Work Environment Dimensions

Various authors have delineated dimensions of the entrepreneurial work environment. Wiklund (1999) outlined three dimensions: innovativeness, proactiveness, and risk-taking. Innovativeness entails supporting novelty and creativity, fostering the development of new ideas through experimentation (Lumpkin & Dess, 1996). Proactiveness involves seeking opportunities not currently present, introducing new ideas, products, or services ahead of competitors (Venkatraman, 1989). Risk-taking refers to the courage to take risks in entrepreneurial activity. These dimensions have been widely used by researchers such as Covin and Slevin (1989), Naman and Slevin (1993), Zahra and Garvis (2000), and Kemelgor (2002).

However, this study adopts Bandura's (1989) autonomy and Wiklund's (1989) innovativeness and risk-taking as dimensions of the entrepreneurial work environment. Hence, the commonly recognized dimensions are risk-taking, innovation, and autonomy/independence.

Risk-Taking Environment

Risk-taking behavior is a fundamental trait of entrepreneurs (Carland et al., 1996), as evidenced by subsequent studies like Tyszka et al. (2011), which found higher levels of risk-taking among entrepreneurs compared to non-entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurs exhibit proactive behavior in assuming risks associated with their activities and take responsibility for outcomes (Dewett, 2006). They are willing to face uncertainty and potential loss as part of their entrepreneurial endeavors (Forlani & Mullins, 2000), influenced by societal and organizational cultures.

Organizational practices can promote risk-taking behavior, with empowering leadership being a key factor (Inceoglu et al., 2018; Martin et al., 2015). Empowering leaders delegate authority, grant autonomy, and involve employees in decision-making processes (Ahearne et al., 2005). Additionally, encouraging risk-taking can involve leading by example, defining smart risks, fostering open communication, creating a safe environment for experimentation, rewarding risk-takers, identifying and recruiting individuals inclined towards risk-taking, starting small and gradually increasing risk levels, and dedicating time for creative brainstorming sessions (Half, 2019).

Innovative Work Environment

Innovation, defined variably by scholars, involves creating and implementing new processes, products, services, or methods to enhance outcomes, efficiency, and quality (Schumpeter, 1934; OECD/Eurostat, 2005; Mulgary & Albury, 2003). It aims to improve existing resources for economic growth and organizational success (Tohidi & Jabbari, 2012; Samuel et al., 2017).

The work environment plays a crucial role in fostering innovation, with studies indicating a significant association between creativity-supportive environments and creative behavior (Dul, 2014). Practical recommendations for promoting innovation include empowering leadership, which involves delegating decision-making authority to employees (Inceoglu et al., 2018; Martin et al., 2015; Rao-Jada et al., 2019). Additionally, organizational practices like leading by example, fostering a supportive culture, promoting innovation, creating conducive physical environments, and providing learning opportunities can enhance innovation (Australian Government,

Autonomy Work Environment

Autonomy is defined differently depending on the context, such as in learning where it refers to self-directed or self-regulated learning, allowing individuals to control their learning pace and choices (Regan, 2003; Lee et al., 2010; White & Fantone, 2010). Similarly, in management, autonomy is described as self-governance or the ability to pursue work goals with one's own resources (Scott, 2009; Werner-Wahl, 2015).

In the workplace, an autonomous environment means being self-governing and free from excessive external control (Forbes & Jermier, 2015). Employees in such environments are granted time, freedom, and independence in carrying out their duties and responsibilities (Burcharth et al., 2017). Research indicates a positive relationship between autonomy and intrinsic motivation, leading to well-being and job satisfaction (Meng & Ma, 2015; University of Birmingham, 2017). Enhanced well-being and job satisfaction enable employees to exhibit creative behavior and improve performance (Çekmecelioglu & Günsel, 2011). Autonomy is also linked to employee work engagement and better job performance, highlighting the importance of creating a supportive work environment (Gagne & Bhawe, 2011; Muecke & Iseke, 2019).

Innovative Work Behavior

Scott and Bruce (1994, 1998) introduced the concept of innovative work behavior (IWB) without providing a clear definition, leading to various interpretations by different authors. Most definitions, including those by Spreitzer (1995), Janssen (2000), and Dorenbosch, Van Engen, and Verhagen (2005), are derived from West and Farr's (1990) definition, emphasizing the creation and application of new ideas or processes. However, De Spiegelare et al. (2014) criticize this focus on novelty alone, proposing a more comprehensive definition that includes idea generation, introduction, and application to benefit the relevant unit.

Thus, innovative work behavior encompasses multiple dimensions, including idea generation, introduction, championing, and application (de Jong & Den Hartog, 2008). While some studies, such as Shanker et al. (2017) and Leong and Rasli (2013), highlight its positive impact on organizational performance, others, like Nguyen et al. (2021), underscore the influence of factors like entrepreneurial culture or work environment. It's crucial for organizations to foster an environment that motivates employees to be innovative, with leadership and entrepreneurial culture being key dimensions worth attention (Purwanto, 2020).

Conceptual Framework

Source: Langer, et.al (2019 and de Jong & Den Hartog. (2008).

Figure 1: the conceptual framework indicates that entrepreneurial work environment like risk-taking, innovativeness and autonomy affects innovative work behaviour in terms of opportunity exploration, idea generation, championing and application of a new idea.

Statement of the Problems

The study ascertained the effect of an entrepreneurial work environment on innovative work behavior. It answered the following questions:

1. What is the entrepreneurial work environment in terms of :
 - a. Risk-taking
 - b. Innovativeness
 - c. autonomy
2. What is the innovative work behaviour in terms of:
 - a. Opportunity exploration
 - b. Idea generation
 - c. championing
 - d. Application of idea
3. Is there a relationship between an entrepreneurial work environment and innovative work behaviour?

Assumption

The study assumes that the work environment affects the innovative work behaviour of employees and performance.

Hypothesis

The study of Nguyen, et al. (2021) suggests that entrepreneurial culture affects innovative work behaviour and based on such findings, the current study also hypothesizes that the entrepreneurial work environment affects the innovative work behaviour of employees.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study covers Divine Word College of Laoag and its employees and it delimits its investigation of the entrepreneurial environment along with the three dimensions: risk-taking, innovativeness, and autonomy, and their effect on innovative work behaviour in terms of opportunity generation, idea generation, championing and the application of the idea.

Research Methodology

Scientific research adheres to established procedures known as research methodology, as noted by Wilkinson (2000) and Leedy (1974). This methodology guides the process of inquiry by applying specific methods to determine, select, and analyze data relevant to the topic under investigation. In line with these principles, the current study employs a defined method of investigation. This includes determining the research design, selecting data gathering instruments, identifying the study population and locale, outlining data gathering procedures, and specifying the statistical treatment of data.

Research Design of the Study

The study employs a descriptive assessment and descriptive correlational research design. According to Ariola (2006), a descriptive correlational study aims to describe relationships among variables without establishing causality. On the other hand, descriptive research seeks to depict a population, situation, or phenomenon, providing insights into profiles, frequency distributions, and characteristics, as outlined by McCombes (2020). In essence, descriptive research addresses the questions of what, when, how, and where, rather than why.

The Locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word College of Laoag. This college is located in Laoag City, the capital of Ilocos Norte.

Population

The study surveyed employees of the college. Due to the limited number of employees, total enumeration sampling was employed, encompassing all faculty and staff members of the college as respondents.

Data Gathering instruments

The study adopted validated questionnaires by Langer, et al., (2019) on the entrepreneurial environment, and de Jong and Den Hartog (2008) on innovative work behaviour (IWB).

Data Gathering Procedures

To uphold ethical standards in scientific research, data collection began upon receiving approval from the college president. The researcher initiated this process by sending a letter to the president, which was duly endorsed. Upon approval, questionnaires were distributed by a designated representative of the researcher. Subsequently, data collection was supervised by the researcher's appointed representative from the college, who then submitted the collected data for tabulation.

Ethical Procedures

The study was carried out after the research ethics committee examined and approved the content of the paper if it did not violate ethical standards and if it did not cause harm to human life and the environment.

The study proceeded after the research ethics committee reviewed and approved the paper to ensure it met ethical standards and posed no harm to people or the environment.

To analyze the data, descriptive and inferential statistics were applied. The weighted mean determined the level of the entrepreneurial environment, covering aspects like risk-taking, innovativeness, autonomy, and innovative work behavior (including opportunity exploration, idea generation, championing, and application of new ideas). ANOVA measured the correlation between the entrepreneurial work environment and innovative work behavior. The data interpretation will be based on predefined ranges.

Statistical Range	Descriptive Interpretation
4.21-5.00	strongly agree/ Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree / High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree/ Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree/Low
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree/Very Low

Presentation of Data and Analysis

The data are presented in the table following the statement of the problems of the study.

Problem 1: What is the entrepreneurial work environment in terms of :

- a. Risk-taking
- b. Innovativeness
- c. autonomy

Table1: Risk-Taking Environment

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
This institution is a very dynamic and entrepreneurial place. People are willing to stick their necks out and take risks.	3.60	A/H
In general, employees are willing to take the risk	3.64	A/H
Employees are trusted and they won't be judged or punished if they fail	3.50	A/H
Instead of focusing on the failure, support and encourage employees to learn from their experiences	3.66	A/H
Offer praise and promotions to those employees who have been brave enough to take calculated risks	3.62	A/H
Encourage employees to come up with new ideas	3.62	A/H
The supervisors lead by their examples through their willingness to challenge the status quo	3.64	A/H
The employees are encouraged to take considered risks to open up opportunities for innovation.	3.68	A/H
Composite Mean	3.62	A/H

Source: Langer, et.al (2019)

Legend:

4.21-5.00 strongly agree/ Very High

3.41-4.20 *Agree / High*
 2.61-3.40. *Somewhat agree/ Moderate*
 1.81-2.60 *Disagree/Low*
 1.00-1.80 *Strongly disagree/Very Low*

Based on the data presented in the table, it is evident that the entrepreneurial work environment at the Divine Word College of Laoag, particularly in terms of the risk-taking dimension, achieved a composite mean rating of 3.62, falling within the "agree/high" category. This assessment aligns with the findings of Langer et al. (2019), indicating a dynamic and encouraging environment that supports risk-taking behavior and fosters innovation. Moreover, Elsayed et al. (2023) suggest that organizations encouraging risk-taking behavior can enhance employee engagement, job satisfaction, and innovative work behavior. Additionally, Jung et al. (2020) assert that such environments promote employees' commitment to organizational change.

Table 2: Innovative Environment

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
Demonstrate positive reception of ideas from others and provide constructive advice.	3.68	A/H
Make innovation an integral part of leadership and management activities.	3.66	A/H
Consult on and establish working conditions that reflect and encourage innovative practice.	3.64	A/H
Introduce and maintain workplace procedures that foster innovation	3.62	A/H
Acknowledge suggestions, improvements and innovations from all colleagues	3.64	A/H
Find appropriate ways of celebrating and promoting innovations	3.62	A/H
Promote and reinforce the value of innovation according to the vision and objective of the institution.	3.66	A/H
Proactively share relevant information, knowledge and skills with colleagues.	3.70	A/H
Composite Mean	3.65	A/H

Source: *Source: Langer, et.al (2019)*

It is evident in data shown that the entrepreneurial work environment, specifically regarding the innovative dimension, received a composite mean rating of 3.65, indicating an "agree/high" level. This suggests that the environment fosters innovation, although not excessively so. Individual indicators also align with this high rating. Employees perceive the workplace as welcoming of new ideas, supportive of innovative practices, and integral to leadership and management (Langer et al., 2019). Research by Abun et al. (2023) and You et al. (2022) further supports the positive correlation between an innovative work environment and employees' innovative behavior.

Table 3: Autonomous Work Environment

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
At work, I feel a sense of choice and freedom in the things I undertake because no one dictates to me what to do.	3.56	A/H
I feel that my decisions in my job reflect what I want because I am the one who sets the rules of my job	3.58	A/H
I feel my choices in my job express who really, I really am because I decide what matters to my job.	3.60	A/H
I feel I have been doing what interests me in my job because I am the one who decides what I want to do with my work.	3.64	A/H
Composite Mean	3.60	A/H

Source: Langer, et.al (2019)

The data in the table indicates that the entrepreneurial work environment, particularly in terms of autonomy, received a composite mean rating of 3.60, signifying a high level. This suggests that while autonomy is not excessively high, it is still regarded positively by employees. They feel empowered to make work-related decisions, contributing to their sense of freedom and choice (Langer et al., 2019). Research by Johansen & Zak (2020) and Khoshnaw & Alavi (2020) supports the notion that job autonomy enhances feelings of achievement, job satisfaction, and performance, fostering a greater sense of ownership over outcomes.

Table 4: Innovative work behaviour of employees (n=151)

	INNOVATIVE WORK BEHAVIOR OF EMPLOYEES	WEIGHTED MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE INTERPRETATION
A	Opportunity Exploration		
1.	I pay attention to issues that are not part of my daily work	3.64	A/H
2.	I wonder how things can be improved	4.09	A/H
	Composite Mean	3.86	A/H
B.	Idea Generation		
1.	I search out new working methods, techniques or instruments	4.19	A/H
2.	I generate original solutions for problems	4.10	A/H
3.	I find new approaches to executing tasks	4.14	A/H
	Composite Mean	4.14	A/H
C.	Championing		
1.	I make important organizational members enthusiastic about innovative ideas	4.04	A/H
2.	I attempt to convince people to support an innovative idea	4.04	A/H
	Composite Mean	4.04	A/H
D.	Application of Idea		
1.	I systematically introduce innovative ideas into work practices	4.04	A/H
2.	I contribute to the implementation of new ideas	4.02	A/H
3.	I put effort into the development of new things	4.09	A/H
	Composite Mean	4.05	A/H
	OVERALL MEAN	4.02	A/H

Source: de Jong & Den Hartog. (2008).

Legend:

Range of Mean Values

4.21 - 5.00

3.41 - 4.20

2.61 - 3.40

1.81 - 2.60

1.00 - 1.80

Descriptive Interpretation

Strongly agree/Very High

Agree/High

Somewhat agree/Moderate

Disagree/Low

Strongly disagree

The data from the table shows that overall, employees' innovative work behavior received a composite mean rating of 4.02, indicating a high level of agreement. This means that while not exceptionally high, the innovative work behavior is regarded positively by employees. They express readiness to explore new opportunities, generate innovative ideas, and implement them to tackle existing challenges (Chan & Rasli, 2014). Research by Choi et al. (2021) and Yuan and Woodman (2010) supports the idea that innovative work behavior correlates positively with work role performance, creativity, and organizational innovation.

Problem 3: Is there a relationship between an entrepreneurial work environment and innovative work behaviour?

Table 5: Entrepreneurial Work Environment and Opportunity Exploration

The combination of risk-taking, innovative, and autonomous work environments does not significantly predict employees' innovative work behavior regarding opportunity exploration ($F(3,147) = 0.973, p > .05$), with only a 1.90% overlap among the predictor variables and opportunity exploration. Thus, differences in employees' innovative work behavior in terms of opportunity exploration cannot be attributed to variations in their entrepreneurial work environment related to risk-taking, innovation, and autonomy.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.140 ^a	.019	-.001	.71130

a. Predictors: (Constant), Autonomous Work Environment, Risk Taking Environment, Innovative Environment

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.477	3	.492	.973	.407 ^b
	Residual	74.374	147	.506		
	Total	75.851	150			

a. Dependent Variable: Opportunity Exploration

b. Predictors: (Constant), Autonomous Work Environment, Risk Taking Environment, Innovative Environment

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.316	.395		10.919	.000
	Risk Taking Environment	-.322	.223	-.255	-1.444	.151
	Innovative Environment	.100	.228	.082	.438	.662
	Autonomous Work Environment	.097	.202	.077	.481	.631

a. Dependent Variable: Opportunity Exploration

Table 6: Entrepreneurial Work Environment and Idea Generation

The entrepreneurial work environment at Divine Word College of Laoag, including factors like risk-taking, innovation, and autonomy, does not significantly predict employees' innovative work behavior in terms of idea generation ($F(3,147)$, $p > .05$). Only 0.04 percent of the variability in idea generation can be attributed to these predictor variables. Therefore, differences in the entrepreneurial work environment are not responsible for the varying levels of innovative work behavior among employees when it comes to generating

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.066 ^a	.004	-.016	.58781

a. Predictors: (Constant), Autonomous Work Environment, Risk Taking Environment, Innovative Environment

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.225	3	.075	.217	.884 ^b
	Residual	50.792	147	.346		
	Total	51.017	150			

a. Dependent Variable: Idea Generation

b. Predictors: (Constant), Autonomous Work Environment, Risk Taking Environment, Innovative Environment

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.239	.327		12.975	.000
	Risk Taking Environment	.056	.184	.054	.303	.762
	Innovative Environment	.050	.188	.051	.267	.790
	Autonomous Work Environment	-.133	.167	-.129	-.795	.428

a. Dependent Variable: Idea Generation

Table 7: Entrepreneurial Work Environment and Championing

The multiple linear regression analysis showed that when considering the entrepreneurial work environment factors of risk-taking, innovation, and autonomy among DWCL employees together, they did not significantly predict the employees' innovative work behavior of championing ($F(3, 147) = 0.212$, $p > .05$). There was only a 0.04 percent overlap between the predictor variables and championing. Therefore, differences

in employees' championing behavior cannot be attributed to variations in their entrepreneurial work environment regarding risk-taking, innovation, and autonomy.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.066 ^a	.004	-.016	.56405

a. Predictors: (Constant), Autonomous Work Environment, Risk Taking Environment, Innovative Environment

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.203	3	.068	.212	.888 ^b
	Residual	46.768	147	.318		
	Total	46.970	150			

a. Dependent Variable: Championing

b. Predictors: (Constant), Autonomous Work Environment, Risk Taking Environment, Innovative Environment

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.261	.313		13.593	.000
	Risk Taking Environment	-.055	.177	-.055	-.310	.757
	Innovative Environment	.058	.181	.061	.323	.747
	Autonomous Work Environment	-.065	.161	-.065	-.404	.687

a. Dependent Variable: Championing

Table: Entrepreneurial Work Environment and Application of Idea

When combining the entrepreneurial work environment factors of risk-taking, innovation, and autonomy among DWCL employees, they did not significantly predict the employees' innovative work behavior in terms of applying ideas ($F(3,147) = 0.334, p > .05$). There was only a 0.07 percent overlap between the predictor variables and the application of ideas. Therefore, differences in employees' application of ideas cannot be attributed to variations in their entrepreneurial work environment regarding risk-taking, innovation, and autonomy.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.082 ^a	.007	-.014	.59160

a. Predictors: (Constant), Autonomous Work Environment, Risk Taking Environment, Innovative Environment

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.351	3	.117	.334	.801 ^b
	Residual	51.448	147	.350		
	Total	51.798	150			

a. Dependent Variable: Application of Idea

b. Predictors: (Constant), Autonomous Work Environment, Risk Taking Environment, Innovative Environment

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.224	.329		12.848	.000
	Risk Taking Environment	-.175	.185	-.168	-.944	.347
	Innovative Environment	.091	.190	.091	.481	.631
	Autonomous Work Environment	.036	.168	.034	.212	.832

a. Dependent Variable: Application of Idea

Results and Discussions

The study findings reveal that while the entrepreneurial work environment, encompassing risk-taking, innovative atmosphere, and autonomy, is moderately high, so too are the levels of innovative work behaviors among employees. However, the analysis of variance indicates that highly innovative work behaviors are not significantly associated with the entrepreneurial work environment. Put simply, there is no clear link between the entrepreneurial work environment and employees' innovative behaviors.

In the context of Divine Word College of Laoag, other organizational factors not examined in this study may contribute to employees' innovative work behavior. These factors could include entrepreneurial leadership (Li et al., 2020; Sarwoko, 2020; Kreiner et al., 2022), self-efficacy (Akkas, 2023), self-leadership (Kor, 2016), organizational creative climate, and knowledge sharing (Munir & Beh, 2019).

Conclusion

The study investigated how an entrepreneurial work environment, including risk-taking, innovation, and autonomy, affects employees' innovative work behavior. Results indicate that both the entrepreneurial work environment and innovative work behavior are high. However, there is no connection between the two; the entrepreneurial environment doesn't influence innovative behavior. Other factors not considered in this study may explain high levels of innovation among employees. Thus, the hypothesis is rejected. :

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